

Stability Constants of Some Rare Earth-chelates of 3-(N,2-hydroxy- α -methyl-benzylidene)imino Propionic Acid

M. R. MALI, D. C. SEHGAL and R. K. MEHTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur (India)

Manuscript received 15 April 1977, revised 5 November 1977,

accepted 14 March 1978

A survey¹⁻³ of the literature has indicated that no work has been done on La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and Gd(III) chelates of 3-(N,2-hydroxy- α -methyl-benzylidene)imino propionic acid ($H_2\beta P$) Schiff base derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and β -alanine. Hence the work on the potentiometric studies of these chelates was undertaken. The measurements were carried out by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁴ at 25°, 30° and 35° in aqueous media ($\mu=0.1M$, 0.05M and 0.01M $NaClO_4$).

For the evaluation of stability constants, the following solutions (total volume 25.0 ml) were titrated against the standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (0.1M) and the titration curves had the usual shapes. (1) 5.0 ml. 0.01M $HClO_4$ +2.5 ml., 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +17.5 ml. water, (2) 5.0 ml., 0.01M $HClO_4$ +2.5 ml. 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +10.0 ml. 0.01M $H_2\beta P$ +7.5 ml. water, and (3) 5.0 ml., 0.01M $HClO_4$ +2.5 ml., 1.0M $NaClO_4$ +10.0 ml., 0.01M $H_2\beta P$ +2.0 ml, 0.01M Metal-ion solution+5.5 ml., water.

The results of the stability constants of the rare earth chelates were obtained at different ionic strengths at 25°, 30° and 35° (Table 1). The formation curves of the metal-chelates suggest the formation of 1 : 2 complexes. The stabilities of the metal-chelates follow the order, La(III)<Ce(III)<Pr(III)<Nd(III)<Sm(III)<Gd(III), which is in accordance with lanthanide contraction.

TABLE-1 DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF $H_2\beta P$ AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ITS RARE EARTH-CHELATES AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS (μ)

Dissociation stability constants	μ at 25°			μ at 30°			μ at 35°		
	0.1 M	0.05 M	0.01 M	0.1 M	0.05 M	0.01 M	0.1 M	0.05 M	0.01 M
					$H_2\beta P$				
$\log K_1^H$	10.93	10.94	10.95	10.89	10.90	10.92	10.86	10.88	10.89
$\log K_2^H$	9.92	8.95	8.96	8.85	8.87	8.89	8.79	8.81	8.88
					La(III)				
$\log K_1$	6.97	6.99	7.00	6.95	6.97	6.99	6.94	6.96	6.98
$\log K_2$	5.35	5.37	5.38	5.34	5.36	5.39	5.33	5.35	5.37
					Ce(III)				
$\log K_1$	7.82	7.84	7.85	7.78	7.80	7.82	7.75	7.76	7.79
$\log K_2$	6.25	6.27	6.28	6.24	6.26	6.28	6.23	6.25	6.27
					Pr(III)				
$\log K_1$	8.31	8.33	8.34	8.29	8.31	8.34	8.27	8.29	8.31
$\log K_2$	6.65	6.67	6.68	6.63	6.65	6.67	6.61	6.63	6.65
					Nd(III)				
$\log K_1$	8.67	8.69	8.70	8.66	8.68	8.70	8.65	8.67	8.69
$\log K_2$	6.90	6.92	6.93	6.88	6.90	6.93	6.86	6.88	6.90
					Sm(III)				
$\log K_1$	9.11	9.13	9.14	9.10	9.12	9.13	9.09	9.11	9.13
$\log K_2$	7.13	7.15	7.17	7.11	7.12	7.13	7.09	7.11	7.13
					Gd(III)				
$\log K_1$	9.46	9.48	9.51	9.41	9.43	9.45	9.36	9.38	9.39
$\log K_2$	7.29	7.31	7.34	7.27	7.29	7.31	7.25	7.27	7.31

Precision pH-meter type OP : 205 No. 837 with glass-calomel assembly was used. $H_2\beta P$ was synthesised by the general procedure reported earlier⁵, m.p. 197°, found C, 63.68; H, 6.19; N, 6.65; calcd. for $C_{11}H_{13}NO_3$. C, 63.76; H, 6.28; N, 6.76%. All the chemicals used were either BDH or Ridiel reagents. The standard solutions of $H_2\beta P$, metal nitrates and sodium perchlorate were prepared in doubly-distilled water.

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